

Organo-Antimony Compounds. Part III.

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The constitution of Brahmachari's "Ureastibamine" has been the subject of controversy. Although Brahmachari in his first paper (*Ind. J. Med. Research*, 1922, 10, 508) regarded the substance as a urea salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid yet in a subsequent communication (*ibid*, 1924, 12, 423) Brahmachari and Das considered it as the carbamino derivative of the ammonium salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid. According to them the reaction proceeds as follows:—

Davies and Underwood (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2595) had shown that the reaction between urea and an amine is a reversible one and proceeds as follows:—

In the process of Brahmachari (*loc. cit.*) a large excess of urea has to be used and the question has been raised why a compound of the type $\text{CO}(\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H}\cdot\text{NH}_4)_2$ has not been isolated. Further the product is still held by some to be an eutectic mixture and not a true chemical compound.

The reaction between urea and the amine seems thus to depend mainly on the urea dearrangement (1). This reaction seems to take

place at 100° while the disubstituted ureas are formed, as shown by Davies and Underwood (*loc. cit.*) by the breaking up of the monourea derivative into the corresponding isocyanate, which takes place only above 168°. It is thus evident that on account of the lower temperature during the reaction the only product is the monourea derivative, or "Ureastibamine."

The constitution of the ureastibamine has also been determined from another standpoint. It is well known that cyanic acid reacts with amine to form a urea derivative.

If to an aqueous solution of the sodium salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid an equivalent quantity of potassium cyanate is added and the solution is then acidified with dilute mineral acid, an almost colourless amorphous product immediately separates which is insoluble in excess of dilute mineral acid and does not give diazo reaction, but vigorous evolution of nitrogen takes place upon the addition of sodium nitrite solution. These behaviours show that the substance is not an amine but an amide, formed according to the following equation:—

When this substance is dissolved in ammonia and a large excess of alcohol is added to the solution, a product separates which cannot be anything but the carbamino-derivative of the ammonium salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid and is identical, both chemically and physiologically, with Brahmachari's ureastibamine. Thus it is definitely proved that ureastibamine is a chemical compound and not a mixture.

The method for the preparation of ureastibamine, as published by Brahmachari (*loc. cit.*) is lacking in experimental details and attempts to prepare it by the published method were not successful. When to a water suspension of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid urea is added, the stibinic acid goes into solution but the product that is precipitated by the addition of alcohol is not the required compound but appears to be the urea salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid. If on the other hand the condensation is carried out in slightly alkaline or acid medium, the product is merely the ammonium salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid. To obtain the true ureastibamine,

the solution of the stibinic acid with urea had to be heated in a boiling water-bath for 3-4 hours.

A remarkable fact was noticed in the course of this work. Urea-stibamine (which is the ammonium salt) is an extremely active agent for the destruction of the kalaazar parasites but the corresponding sodium and potassium salts, although less toxic and more stable, are without any marked action.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The preparation of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid has been described previously (Niyogy, this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 285).

Condensation of 4-Aminophenyl stibinic Acid and Urea.

(a) *In neutral solution.*—4-Aminophenyl stibinic acid (about 4 gms.) was suspended in water (50 c.c) and to this was gradually added solid urea (about 20 gms.) till the whole of the stibinic acid had gone into solution. It was sometimes necessary to warm the reaction mixture on a water-bath during the addition of urea. This solution was then filtered and treated with a large excess of alcohol. A gelatinious precipitate separated which was filtered off, washed with absolute alcohol till free from urea, and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride; yield about 3 gms.

Properties.—It dissolved in water forming a red solution. On adding dilute acetic acid to the water solution the free acid separated which dissolved readily when a few drops of hydrochloric acid were added. It gave the diazo reaction. Apparently the substance had a free amino group and could not be ureastibamine. (Found: C, 25.78; Sb, 37.48. $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{SbO}_3\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, requires C, 26.09; Sb, 37.2 per cent.)

(b) *In presence of acetic acid.*—The condensation was carried out as described before but a small quantity of acetic acid was added to the suspension of the stibinic acid, before the addition of urea, and the solution was heated on a water-bath for half an hour. The product now obtained had identical properties with the compound described before but the analytical data showed it to be the ammonium salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid. (Found: C, 25.27; Sb, 42.7. $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{SbO}_3\text{H} \cdot \text{NH}_4$ requires C, 25.9; Sb, 43 per cent.)

Preparation of the Ammonium Salt of 4-Carbamido-phenyl stibinic Acid.

4-Aminophenyl stibinic acid (about 4 gms.) in water suspension was treated with solid urea and the reaction vessel was heated in a boiling water-bath for 3-4 hours and left overnight. The solution was then filtered off from the separated solids and again allowed to stand overnight. This was again filtered from separated solids, if any, and treated with a large excess of alcohol, when an almost colourless amorphous substance separated. This precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered, and washed repeatedly with alcohol till free from urea and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride. (Found: C, 25.45; Sb, 36.6. NH_2 . CO. NH. C_6H_4 SbO_3H . NH_4 requires C, 26.09; Sb, 37.2 per cent).

Properties.—It dissolved easily in water forming a red solution. With dilute acetic acid the solution gave a precipitate which did not dissolve in excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. It did not give diazo reaction but nitrogen was given off when the acid solution was treated with sodium nitrite.

The analytical data as well as the chemical properties of the solution correspond with Brahmachari's ureastibamine.

Preparation of the above Compound from the Sodium Salt of 4-Aminophenyl stibinic Acid and Potassium Cyanate.

Sodium salt of 4-aminophenyl stibinic acid (6 gms.) was dissolved in water (50 c. c.) and potassium cyanate (3 gms.) was added to it. To the cold solution acetic acid (6 c. c.) was gradually added. A light brown precipitate separated, which was shaken for sometime and allowed to stand overnight. To the contents of the flask hydrochloric acid (10 c. c., d1.12) was added and thoroughly mixed. The precipitate was then filtered off, washed till free from acid, and suspended in water. The water suspension was divided into three parts. To the first portion dilute ammonium hydroxide was added drop by drop till the whole of the suspended solid had gone into solution. This was allowed to stand overnight, filtered off and treated with a large excess of alcohol. The precipitate that now separated was identical, both in chemical and physiological properties, with Brahmachari's ureastibamine. (Found: C, 25.82; Sb,

36.91. NH_2 . CO. NH. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{H.NH}_4$ requires C, 26.09; Sb, 37.2 per cent.)

The second portion was well cooled in ice, and cold dilute caustic soda was very slowly added till the whole of the solid had dissolved (avoid excess of alkali). The solution was then allowed to stand for some hours, filtered and treated with an excess of alcohol when the sodium salt separated. (Found: Na, 7.21; Sb, 36.2. NH_2 . CO. NH. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{HNa}$, requires Na, 7.03; Sb, 36.7 per cent.)

The third portion was similarly treated with caustic potash when the potassium salt was obtained. (Found: K, 11.56; Sb, 34.61. NH_2 . CO. NH. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SbO}_3\text{HK}$ requires K, 11.3; Sb, 34.98 per cent.)

I desire to convey my thanks to Prof. H. K. Sen for the interest he has taken in this work.

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Received October 2, 1928.

